

CURRENT SITUATION AND TRENDS IN EUROPEAN MARTIAL ARTS RESEARCH

(based on the report at the Japanese Budo Academy and IMACSSS conference in Osaka '2023).

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Abstract

Problem: Budō and other Asian martial arts have been practised in Europe since the late 1800s. All fighting arts are also a subject matter of scientific research. The following research questions have been formulated: What is the current situation of martial arts research in Europe? What are trends in European martial arts research? What academic institutions operate in this area?

Method: The literature covering this subject matter was reviewed and a topic-related search in scientific databases was carried out. The contents of websites of major scientific periodicals and databases i.e., Web of Science and Scopus were examined taking into account the thematic profile "martial arts". Additionally, Impact Factor report (Web of Science) for the year 2023 was analysed.

Results: Five specialist scientific journals were identified; four of these continue to operate today. The dominant theoretical approaches and problem areas were reviewed along with the most frequently published contents.

Conclusions: The predominant trend in research is related to sport studies. This is an effect of the fact that many traditional martial arts have largely been associated with sport. Academic research focusing on cultural, historical and philosophical aspects of Budō and other fighting arts is less common.

Keywords: fighting arts, *Budo*, General Theory, European research, scientific institution

Introduction

Martial arts, including Japanese *budō*, are practiced in many countries worldwide. This is true about both the forms of *jutsu* (emphasis to the technical aspects, technical and tactical skills, and practical applications), and *dō*. These are cultivated as a sport and physical recreation, because of their values from the viewpoint of pedagogy (physical education) and health (motor rehabilitation), or in the

entire spectrum of physical culture (Cynarski et al., 2014). They are used in the uniformed services and in civilian self-defence. They are also practised in their original version, to cultivate the traditions of the old schools (*koryū*) and as avenues for self-realisation - to improve the character/personality of the practitioners. Today this is the case worldwide, including in the countries of Western culture, particularly in Europe.

The phenomenon of the worldwide popularity of martial arts is being investigated by the academic community of many countries around the world. This applies to the countries of their origin, but not only. In Europe, too, and in Poland in particular, it is an area of interest to scholars, especially those associated within IMACSSS (International Martial Arts and Combat Sports Scientific Society), IPA (Idokan Poland Association) and those connected with several scientific journals.

The following sections point to the research problem and the method applied; they present theoretical approaches and the fact that explicit determination of theoretical perspective is being avoided; they define three problem areas of the study; they identify the predominant themes and the specific paradigms of academic requirements or preferences of the major specialist scientific periodicals.

The author favours the General Theory of Fighting Arts as an approach satisfying the objectives of the new paradigm – the systematic, cultural and humanistic viewpoints appropriate for the 21st century. The term fighting arts is a broad concept covering martial arts, combat sports, self-defence systems, combat systems and the related forms (Cynarski 2019).

The search for the presence of the term "martial arts research" in scientific literature, conducted in Web of Science Core Collection (global range), produced 1,102 results. These are mainly the publications in "Ido Movement for Culture", "Revista de Artes Marciales Asiáticas" (RAMA), as well as various conference proceedings, and others. The same search in Scopus database produced 38 document results – mainly conference proceedings and articles in various journals.

The search for the term "martial arts from European perspective" in Web of Science produced only 15 results, including 8 in "Ido Movement for Culture". In Scopus database, zero results were found. In this database the author used the key words: "martial arts, European". The search engine showed 11 works published in a variety of scientific journals.

Problem and Method

The research problem was defined as reflected by the following three specific questions: 1) What is the current situation of martial arts research in Europe? 2) What are trends in European martial arts research? 3) What academic institutions operate in this area? An attempt was made to find answers to the questions formulated this way.

Analysis of the literature covering this subject matter was applied (Krippendorf 2004; Green et al., 2019) along with a topic-related search in scientific databases. The websites of scientific periodicals of major importance for the subject matter of the study were investigated for the contents. On 20 April 2023 the author examined the most important scientific databases – Web of Science and Scopus – taking into account the key words and issues. Particular attention was paid to the most important scientific journals published in Europe, with thematic profiles covering "martial arts". Additionally, the report by Clarivate Analytics was reviewed to examine the most important evaluation index, i.e., Impact Factor (Web of Science) for the year 2022 published in June 2023.

1. What theory?

The works by European authors are found to apply various theoretical approaches, or quite often no specific theory (scientific framework) is defined. Social, pedagogical or cultural studies more commonly present such explicit information. In empirical research, we usually find contributions without reference to a particular scientific theory. By implication, these are studies based on generally accepted canons / paradigms in the specific discipline or sub-discipline.

Martial arts are investigated in line with approaches which could be referred to as humanistic (ranging from philosophy, history, and sociology, to psychology and pedagogy), and bio-medical (health sciences, as well as sport and physical culture studies, and other) and in course of interdisciplinary research. Interdisciplinary approach seems to be the most cognitively promising in the area of fighting arts.

Research in the area of science / empirical studies relates mainly to the area of sport science / sport sciences, human movement or physical culture sciences. In this case, martial arts are investigated in the same way as the other sport disciplines. The knowledge of training theory and sport combat theory, movement teaching methodology, exercise physiology, principles of supplementation and biological wellness increases the effects of the training process and results in combat sports.

Conversely, humanistic, cultural and social studies do not have such a direct bearing on sporting performance, although the cultural context and especially the psychological aspects are important. In top-level competitive sport, it is this psychological factor that is sometimes decisive. On the other hand, however, unlike combat sports, the classical martial arts (which reject competition) are impossible to understand without humanistic/cultural research.

Treatises, monographs and textbooks present different approaches. Their theoretical basis is not always referred to explicitly. It also happens that the theory is being consistently developed. This is how, based on the Humanistic Theory of Martial Arts (Cynarski, Obodyński 2003; Cynarski 2004, 2006) and on anthropology of martial arts (Cynarski 2012a, 2012b), the **General Theory of**

Fighting Arts was developed (Cynarski 2019). A series of books, based on this theory include monographs and academic coursebooks, such as:

Martial Arts Anthropology, Participants' Motivation and Behaviours (Zeng et al., 2013);

Participation Motivations of Taekwondo Athletes / Students (Zeng, Cynarski 2016);

Tourism of martial Arts: social-cultural perspective (Cynarski 2020);

Lexicon of fighting arts. Masters and their schools (Cynarski 2021);

Philosophy of Martial Arts (Cynarski 2022);

Sociology of Fighting Arts (Cynarski 2023).

Thus, these are findings of pedagogical, sociological, anthropological/cultural, historical and philosophical research, at the same time taking into account the perspective of sports science/physical culture sciences.

In other approaches this is for instance the concept of *martial arts studies* proposed by P. Bowman (Bowman 2015), and referred to by G. Jennings (Jennings 2023) and collaborators of the journal with the same name. Bowman (Bowman 2021) on the other hand, refers mainly to trendy European sociologists and other social scientists. In contrast, studies carried out for the needs of sport/physical culture, usually make only references to the state of knowledge in the light of empirical research and the established canon (paradigm) in areas of coaching and kinesiology, human kinetics or biomechanics, psychology of sport, sports medicine, physical education, etc.

2. Problem areas investigated

The subject matter of research includes the original **Asian Martial Arts**, as well as martial arts and combat sport derived from these; **Historical European Martial Arts (HEMA)** and other **European fighting arts**; other, **different Fighting Arts**. Problems investigated in the case of combat sports are related to training and its optimisation, the determinants of sporting achievement (links to psychology, physiology, biomechanics etc.), and the principles of teaching (Arziutov et al., 2016). In martial arts and self-defence systems, the subject matter often relates to teaching methodology, technical and tactical issues, as well as history, specific philosophy and cultural contexts.

- Research about **Asian Martial Arts** in Europe

Seemingly, the largest number of papers are concerned with *judo* as a globally popular, Olympic sport. These are particularly works in the area of sports science, in Europe and East Asia alike (Iteya et al., 2011; Korobeynikov et al., 2021; Reis et al., 2022). Furthermore, currently conducted studies investigate historical presence of budo in Europe (Grzegorz, Walendowicz 2008; Sikorski 2009; Kraska 2020; Pérez-Gutiérrez et al. 2021), martial arts from the standpoint of the theory of cultural dialogues (Tokarski 1989; Cynarski 2000; Cynarski, Huzarska 2011), involvement of

martial arts in the process of cultural globalisation (Cynarski 2002, 2003; Bowman 2010; Kraska 2020), and the process of reinventing these (Jennings 2023).

Academic considerations also address the border areas between martial arts and mass culture, and the relationships between these areas of culture (Cynarski 2000; Bowman 2021). In the case of the book by Bowman, there is equivalence between mass culture and popular culture, which is not correct. And his book is more about the perception of martial arts from an American perspective. *Budo* in Europe and from European perspective is discussed e.g., in a series of books published in Poland (Sikorski, Tokarski 1988; Cynarski 2000, 2004, 2006), and in Polish language therefore they are fairly unknown by readers abroad. These contain a multifaceted presentation of martial arts and their presence ranging from mass culture to symbolic culture and the world of values (axiosphere).

- Research about **HEMA** in Europe

The European chivalric traditions, as well as historical fencing, are referred to as HEMA – Historical European Martial Arts. In this case, the historical sources are investigated along with the construction and practical qualities of the weapon, and the use of the weapon especially in duelling (Demesy 2015; Jaquet 2016; Jennings 2023). These are traditions common to much of medieval Europe. "Knightly combat" has now become a sporting discipline - a special kind of team combat sport (confrontation 3 vs. 3, 5 vs. 5, 16 vs. 16 or 21 vs. 21). Knights' brotherhoods and re-enactment groups present historical battles. Knights' tournaments are also reactivated.

In Western Europe, the rapier and later the sword became popular. In Poland, it is especially the cultivation of Old Polish hussar sabre fencing and the sabre-style "*Sztuka Cięć Krzyżowych*" / Cross Cutting Art (Starzewski School (Borysiuk et al., 2013), Zabłocki School (Cynarski 2008), and *Signum Polonicum* (Sawicki 2011]). The history of the wooden practice weapon - the so-called *palcat* - is also quite well described. *Palcat* was used to prepare Polish noblemen to fight with sabres (Sawicki 2020).

Other martial art traditions, such as e.g. the Ukrainian *Boiovyi hopak* (combat *hopak*) (Pilat et al., 2022), are increasingly recognised as an important component of cultural heritage contributing to the development of national pride/identity. Breton and Celtic wrestling, Italian and Portuguese stick fighting, and other national or regional traditions are being cultivated.

- Research about other / all / **different Fighting Arts**

Interesting areas of research include martial arts of Japanese provenance, but created in Europe:

1. *Jujutsu* as a self-defence system – practiced in Europe from the late 19th/early 20th century, with an example of Erich Rahn and his schools in Berlin (year 1906) (Preiss 2012; Kraska 2020]. This is more or less modernised type of *jujutsu*.
2. Austrian *judo-do* (Klinger-Klingerstorff 1951; Cynarski 2021), which was an advancement from the original *judo*.

3. Modern German *jujutsu* / *Wettkampfsport* (Kulot 1986; Renninghoff, Witte 1998). This is a modern type of sport, spreading internationally. Sports *jujutsu* – in this case research is carried out mainly from the perspective of sport theory (Ambrozy et al., 2014; Ambroży et al., 2021).

Studies focus on original martial arts from East and Southeast Asia, as well as the martial arts of Brazil (*capoeira* and the so-called Bjj – Brazilian *jiu-jitsu*) and many others. Specific related phenomena include martial arts tourism. Research in this area focuses on journeys between Europe and East Asia (Cynarski 2020; Pawelec et al., 2020; Figueiredo et al., 2020).

Like generally in the social sciences, in the case of social research in martial arts there is an entanglement with trendy ideologies and other mass culture trends. Hence, we can find analyses focusing on martial arts & gender (Channon 2014). The trends related to Mixed Martial Arts (MMA) provoke research related to this type of show (Spencer 2009; Silva *et al.* 2016). The author once referred to it as modern day gladiatorship (Cynarski, Litwiniuk 2006).

3. What is published and where? What themes are predominant?

There are few academic journals in Europe with a thematic profile covering martial arts. The most important can be distinguished (chronologically, according to the year they were started):

1. "Ido Movement for Culture. Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology" (Rzeszów, Poland, published continuously since 2000) – covers a wide range of research in fighting arts, according to the General Theory of Fighting Arts. It is published by Idokan Poland Association (IPA) and the Yoshin Academy.
2. "Archives of Budo" (Warsaw, Poland, - since 2005) – essentially focusing on sport sciences, combat sports (boxing, wrestling, as well as *judo*, and others). It is a commercial publication.
3. "Revista de Artes Marciales Asiáticas" (RAMA) (Leon, Spain, - since 2006) – like "Ido Movement for Culture", it covers a wide range of research in fighting arts. It is published by the University de Leon.
4. "Martial Arts Studies" (Cardiff, UK, - since 2015) - publishes the highest quality academic work on any aspect of martial arts studies, like cultural studies. It is published by Cardiff University Press.

These journals keep evolving and changing. Some periodicals close down and disappear from the "academic market", like "Journal of Combat Sports and Martial Arts" which was published in Poland for a few years (Cynarski, Reguli 2014; Pawelec 2016; Gutierrez-Garcia et al., 2018; Raimondo et al, 2021). Their current status (according to IF for 2023) is shown in Table 1. The highest Impact Factor was calculated for "Archives of Budo" (IF: 1.4). Notably, "Archives of Budo"

is a highly commercial journal, with a cost for publication of an article amounts to 2,800 USD plus VAT (as of 26 May 2023).

Table 1. The best European journals in the area of martial arts research

Number	Name of journal	Country of publishing	Published since	Indexation / Impact Factor
1	Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology	Poland	2000-	Scopus, Web of Science / IF 2022: 1.0; 2023: 0.8
2	Archives of Budo	Poland	2005-	Scopus, Web of Science / IF 2022: 2.1; 2023: 1.4
3	Revista de Artes Marciales Asiáticas	Spain	2006-	Scopus, Web of Science / no IF; 2023: 1.0
4	Martial Arts Studies	Wales / UK	2015-	no data / not indexed
5	Journal of Combat Sports and Martial Arts	Poland	2009-2017	no data / no longer operating

[Source: the author's own research]

Very interesting issues are investigated in course of interdisciplinary studies carried out e.g., by Georgiy Korobeynikov's team. The research covers areas related to psychology, physiology and motor skills (neurodynamics, psychophysiological state, nervous system, aggression, technical and tactical decisions during combat) (Korobeynikov et al., 2019; Korobeynikov et al., 2021; Korobeynikov et al., 2022; Korobeinikova et al., 2020). These are only a few works presenting results of these studies, and published in "*Ido Movement for Culture*". The latter scientific journal publishes works covering a rather wide range of issues, from Kinesiology & Coaching, to Martial Arts Tourism and cultural studies.

Very interesting works are also published in special editions of other periodicals. One example is the journal *Applied Sciences* and its Special Issue "Athletes Performance and Analysis in Combat Sports and Martial Arts". Here the guest editors are (in the alphabetical order): T. Ambroży, W.

Błach, W.J. Cynarski, W. Czarny and Ł. Rydzik, all five from Poland, and articles are published by many authors from various countries, representing sport sciences.

"RAMA" in the past used to publish various historical and cultural studies. Today these are mainly empirical studies related to sport sciences. The area of cultural / humanistic studies is the domain of the British journal "Martial Arts Studies". Here we find qualitative research - discussions and essays, as well as historical studies focusing on various martial arts.

One cannot overlook the annual conferences of IMACSSS – International Martial Arts and Combat Sports Scientific Society. The published proceedings and abstracts from the specific conferences contribute to the body of knowledge by presenting the contents of discussions held at what may be the most important meetings of researchers specialising in the multifactorial phenomenon of fighting arts or in its specific components. The status of research and overview of the publications are regularly monitored by the quarterly "Ido Movement for Culture Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology" (Bartik et al., 2020).

Summary

In response to the two questions: 1) What is current situation of martial arts research in Europe? and, 3) What academic institutions operate in this area?, it is possible to say that the cultural phenomenon of fighting arts, especially martial arts of Japanese origin, has been the subject of scientific research by several specialised academic institutions. These are the scientific societies, such as IPA and IMACSSS, and a number of high quality scientific journals. Both scientific societies and editorial boards of the scientific journals enable the presentation of research findings, their publication and discussion - at scientific conferences.

"2nd question: What are trends in European martial arts research?" The predominant trend in research is related to sport studies. This is an effect of the fact that many traditional martial arts have largely been associated with sport. Academic research focusing on cultural, historical and philosophical aspects of *budō* and other fighting arts is less common.

Significantly, a major location for research, publications and conference meetings in Europe is Poland - a country at the geographical centre of the continent.

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